

A 'global iteration' process using intermediate astrometry

L Lindegren (SAG_LL_018.txt, 3 June 1998)

Introduction

Concepts for the GAIA data processing may be tested by means of a simplified model using Hipparcos intermediate astrometric data. Aspects of the GAIA data processing that can be tested in this way include:

- * the definition of a number of subject areas with one or several classes in each area, and with some (realistic) degree of complex relations between them;
- * the management of all this within a database;
- * flexibility in modifying or adding to the structure, e.g. by introducing new sub-classes;
- * overall speed and convergence of the 'global iteration' scheme.

All this takes place on a scale which is roughly 10,000 times smaller than the actual GAIA data processing, but should nevertheless be an interesting exercise. This note provides a first outline of the proposed model.

Analogue

The correspondence between GAIA data and the Hipparcos intermediate astrometry is outlined below. The approximate data volumes (number of reals) are indicated in parentheses.

GAIA	Hipparcos intermediate astrometry
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Data:

telemetry data (1E+14)	(see below)
raw objects (1E+12)	abscissae (3E+07) [one consortium]
attitude data (2E+06)	great-circle harmonics (4E+04)
calibration data (1E+07)	chromaticity data (1000)
star catalogue (2E+10)	star catalogue (1E+06)

Processes:

astrometry	astrometry
attitude determination	determination of harmonics
instrument calibration	determination of chromaticity

There is no analogue to the GAIA raw data (telemetry) stream, as the

abscissae are already sorted according to HIP number and thus correspond to a GAIA 'raw object'. It is not clear if one would actually sort the GAIA data in this way, or keep them in the original (chronological) order, or even maintain both orderings in parallel. This choice – which has to do with the physical rather than logical implementation of the model – could have a profound impact on the performance. The present model could be used to test this.

Outline of the data

Abscissae: the structure of this data set corresponds to IH and IA, although only for one consortium (e.g. FAST). In IH, a colour index (from H40) needs to be added. In IA, the approximate abscissa (from 0 to 360 deg) needs to be calculated and added. IA2 and IA10 are not needed.

Harmonics: this consists of a list of (significant) harmonics for each reference great circle. Its structure could be:

- a header consisting of IR1 to IR4 plus IR8 = number of subsequent harmonics
- for each harmonic (1 to IR8): n = harmonic order, c = cosine coefficient, s = sine coefficient

Chromaticity: this consists of the mean abscissa residual for a given time interval and colour interval. A suitable time interval could be one month (thus some 36 such intervals over the mission) and the colour range ($V-I = -0.3$ to 3) could be divided in 30 or so intervals. For each time/colour bin one needs perhaps four numbers to characterise the distribution of residuals (e.g. 10th, 50th and 90th percentiles, and the number of residuals in the bin).

Star catalogue: to begin with this could contain only single stars (with the provision for adding more complex objects, e.g. orbital binaries, at a later stage). The required data basically correspond to Fields H1, H8–H30.

Outline of the processing

Astrometry: this consists of a robust least-squares fitting of the astrometric parameters in the object model to the abscissa residuals, after correction for the harmonics and chromaticity.

Determination of harmonics: this consists of a robust least-squares fitting of harmonics to the abscissa residuals as function of abscissa, for each great circle separately, after correction for the astrometric parameters and chromaticity.

Determination of chromaticity: this is just a statistical characterisation of the abscissa residuals, after correction for the astrometric parameters and harmonics, according to time and colour.

The required algorithms can readily be provided (in the form of Fortran subroutines).